

Heart Diseases and Stress Prediction Using Machine Learning

Anjali.C.Abraham

PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications

Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirapally,India

anjalicabraham2022a@gmail.com

Meera Rose Mathew

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Applications

Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirapally,India

meerarosemathew@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract- According to a study, 1 in 4 people died from cardiovascular disease. Early diagnosis of these diseases can help prevent death by raising awareness of the condition of the heart. Heart disease can be caused by daily habits. Smoking and drinking can also lead to heart disease. Emotional or physical tension can cause stress. It can happen from an event or a situation. In the paper we are taking a dataset with basic habits and situations that make a person stressed. In the dataset our day-to-day habits are also taken care of for the prediction which help us get a proper prediction about situation of the user, If the user is in stress or not. There are many people with hereditary heart diseases. Depression can be due to life situations and failure. Here, two datasets are used: heart & stress. In the heart.csv, the parameters are age, gender, weight, chest pain, thal, ca, cholesterol, blood sugar, blood pressure, maximum heart rate and in stress.csv, the parameter that taken are anxiety, headache, smoking, sleeping trouble etc. Prediction can be done with the help of an accurate naive bayes and KNN algorithm with 0.56 and 0.97 accuracy.

Keywords:- Heart diseases, age, smoking, gender, stress, cardiovascular diseases, naïve bayes, KNN.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning can be defined as identifying patterns, functions, or conclusions from a different set of data to automatically calculate similar tasks and solve statistical problems. The importance of machine learning in medicine lies in its ability to process large datasets and provide analysis of the data. This helps physicians plan and deliver care, ultimately reducing care costs and increasing life expectancy for patients. The dataset contains values that predict both heart disease and mental health. It can be predicted from

various values such as blood pressure, headache, heart rate, and cholesterol. Those

who predict heart disease or stress should also check their daily activities, such as smoking, if they are alcoholics.

Both affect heart disease and stress. The main reason for this approach is that people suffering from heart disease are more likely to be stressed.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] Any serious disorder that affects the heart is referred to as cardiovascular disease. Because cardiac disorders can be fatal, researchers are working on developing smart systems that employ machine learning algorithms to effectively identify them based on electronic health data. Several machine learning algorithms for predicting cardiac illnesses utilising data from main health indicators from patients are presented in this paper. The prediction models were built using four classification methods: Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Naive Bayes (NB). [2] Heart disease can be prevented with accurate prediction, but it can also be fatal if the prediction is erroneous. The results and analyses of the UCI Machine Learning Heart Disease dataset are compared in this study using various machine learning methods including deep learning. The dataset contains 14 key attributes that were used in the analysis. The accuracy and confusion matrix are used to validate a number of promising outcomes. Isolation Forest is used to manage some unimportant aspects in the dataset, and the data is also standardised for better results. It is also mentioned how this study might be coupled with multimedia technology such as mobile devices. 94.2 percent accuracy was achieved using a deep learning method. [3] Support vector machines, logistic regression, random forest, and ensemble learning are examples of machine learning algorithms that can provide logical reasoning on which to base our predictions. A heart sound categorization model based on heart sounds can help any physician, radiologist, or patient assess the present state of their heart, allowing for more accurate diagnosis on the side of the medical practitioner. The model is based on S1 (lub) and S2 (dub) heart sounds, and it classifies the heart sound to determine how much of it may be categorised as normal, murmur, or extrasystole.[4] Heart disease is one of the top causes of death around the world. In today's typical modern life, deaths from heart disease have become one of the biggest challenges, with around one person dying from heart disease every minute.

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find out if a person is suffering from heart disease or stress. This is done using the naive Bayes algorithm. Two records are combined to form one record with a common column value. The main function does the following :

- Read the data from the user first, then pass the data from the form to the Python file.
- In a Python file, get the data and make it an np array type.
- Then use the panda to read the dataset.
- Next, train the dataset, then create a train test split for the dataset, and then train the dataset.
- Next, adjust the record.
- Convert the data read from the user.
- You can then predict the output and print the accuracy and output on the next screen.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the face detection. While building the model user use the algorithm The steps involved are:

1. We create a form for reading data from the user. Then we create the python file for processing the input that we get from the user and predict if they are having heart diseases or stress

2. Importing the packages:

```
from flask import Flask, request, render_template
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn import metrics
import numpy as np, pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
```

3. We load the data set that is needed for the prediction

```
df = pd.read_csv('heart.csv', header=None)
df1 = pd.read_csv('stress.csv', header=None)
```

4. Then we divide the dataset into two portions and create two np arrays with it.

```
training_X = df.iloc[1:df.shape[0], 0:10]
training_y = df.iloc[1:df.shape[0], 11]
X = np.array(training_X)
y = np.array(training_y)

training_X1 = df1.iloc[1:df1.shape[0], 0:4]
training_y1 = df1.iloc[1:df1.shape[0], 4]
X1 = np.array(training_X1)
y1 = np.array(training_y1)
```

5. Then we create the train test split of the given dataset for an accurate prediction

```
X_train1, X_test1, y_train1, y_test1 = train_test_split(X1, y1, test_size=0.2, random_state=None)
gnb = GaussianNB()
```

6. Then we create an out of the gaussianNB and with the help of this object we fit the dataset for prediction

```
gnb = GaussianNB()
gnb.fit(X_train, y_train.ravel())
```

7. After the fitting is done we predict the out put with the help of the input that we get from the user

```
gnb.fit(X_train, y_train.ravel())
p1 = np.array(final_input).reshape(1, -1)
print(p1)
y_pred1 = gnb.predict(X_test1)
print("xtest", X_test1[0])
pred1 = gnb.predict(p1)
```

8. We have also done the K-NN for both heart and stress , then we have found the score of both the heart and stress

```
knn_scores=[]
for k in range(1,21):
    knn_clf=KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=k)
    knn_clf.fit(X_train,y_train.ravel())
    knn_scores.append(knn_clf.score(X_test,y_test))
p = np.array(final_input1).reshape(1, -1)
print("predict",p)

knn_scoresa = []
for k in range(1, 21):
    knn_clfs = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=k)
    knn_clfs.fit(X_train1, y_train1.ravel())
    knn_scoresa.append(knn_clfs.score(X_test1, y_test1))
p1 = np.array(final_input2).reshape(1, -1)
print(p1)
```

9. After that we find the accuracy of the prediction and also the precision, recall and F-measure is also calculated

```
accb = metrics.accuracy_score(y_test1, y_p)
accA = metrics.accuracy_score(y_test1, y_pred1)
acc1 = (accb+accA)/2
```

10. After finding the accuracy of the prediction we print the output to an html form where the user can view it

```
if pred[0] == '0' and pred1[0] == '0':
    return render_template('index2.html', output1:
elif pred[0] == '1' and pred1[0] == '0':
    return render_template('index2.html', output1:
elif pred[0] == '0' and pred1[0] == '1':
    return render_template('index2.html', output1:
else:
    return render_template('index2.html', output1:
```

11. Then we plot graph of score which we get from KNN

```
plt.scatter([k for k in range(1, 21)], knn_scores, color='red')
for i in range(1, 21):
    plt.text(i, round(knn_scores[i-1], 2), (i, round(knn_scores[i-1], 2)))
plt.xticks([i for i in range(1, 21)])
plt.xlabel('Number of Neighbors (K)')
plt.ylabel('Scores')
plt.title('K-Neighbors Classifier scores for different K values in heart diseases')
plt.show()

plt.scatter([k for k in range(1, 21)], knn_scoresA, color='red')
for i in range(1, 21):
    plt.text(i, round(knn_scoresA[i - 1], 2), (i, round(knn_scoresA[i - 1], 2)))
plt.xticks([i for i in range(1, 21)])
plt.xlabel('Number of Neighbors (K)')
plt.ylabel('Scores')
plt.title('K-Neighbors Classifier scores for different K values in Stress')
plt.show()
```

V. RESULT

We create a form to read the data from the user like heart beat rate, blood pressure and other habits like smoking and alcohol. With the help of the input given by the user and also the dataset we predict if the person is having heart diseases and stress.

Patient Details

Gender	Female
Weight	45
Blood Pressure	100
Blood Sugar	Yes
Maximum-Heart Rate	115
CA	1
Smoking	Yes
Sleeping Trouble	No

Age	22
Chest Pain	Yes
Cholestrol	109
ECG	Medium
Angina	No
Thalassemia	Normal
Headache	Yes
Do you have Anxiety?	No

Figure:1

The above shown is the input screen where we read the data from the user.

Figure:2.1

Figure:2.2

The above graphs shows the score of K-Neighbors for random k values taken from the two datasets.

Prediction

There is a chance of both heart diseases and stress

Using Naive bayes Algorithm :

Accuracy of heart disease : 0.8571428571428571

Accuracy of stress : 1.0

Using K-NN Algorithm :

Accuracy of heart disease : 0.8095238095238095

Accuracy of stress : 0.8571428571428571

Figure:3

The above shown is the prediction screen which shows if the person is having heart diseases and stress or any of these. This prediction is done using naïve bayes and knn algorithms with the help of datasets which contain readings related to heart diseases and stress.

VI. CONCLUSION

The task of predicting heart diseases and stress is really important nowadays because in todays world people are moving so fast that they forget to take care of their health. As health is much important we should reduce stress because it causes many issue in our day today life. If we can predict that a person is having stress then they can take proper medication on time to overcome the issues faced by this problem. Heart

diseases are becoming common these days so getting a checkup once in a while is really important. If a person is having any heart diseases then they will be stressed because it effects their life and also the happiness of the people around them, knowing about this earlier and taking proper medication can help people stay happy and healthy. We can know the accuracy of a person getting affected by stress or heart diseases. So that they can be aware of their condition and also can consult the required medications.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Heart Disease Prediction Using Machine Learning", Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences (ASET) by Chaimaa Boukhatem, Heba Yahia Youssef, Ali Bou Nassif.
- [2] "Heart Disease Prediction using Machine Learning Techniques", 2nd International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication Control and Networking (ICACCCN) by Vijeta Sharma, Shrinkhala Yadav, Manjari Gupta.
- [3] "Heart Health Classification and Prediction Using Machine Learning", 2020 International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) by Hardi Rathod¹, Pratik Kumar Singh², Nikita Tikone³, Suresh Babu⁴ Technology.
- [4] "Machine Learning Based Heart Disease Prediction System", International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI) by M. Snehith Raja, M. Anurag, Ch. Prachetan Reddy, Nageswara Rao Sirisala.
- [5] "Prediction of Heart Disease and Diabetes Using Naive Bayes Algorithm", International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology by Ninad Marathe, Sushopti Gawade, Adarsh Kanekar.